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DEVELOPMENT OF A CRICOTHYROTOMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING MODULE: A
DELPHI ANALYSIS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Cricothyrotomy is categorized as a high acuity, low occurrence critical airway procedure. Because anesthesia providers infrequently perform this airway management technique, there may be some hesitation and uncertainty to begin the procedure, and they may not maintain the skills necessary to successfully complete it. Without frequent airway training, there is a significant decrease in skill performance, adherence to difficult airway algorithms, and timely decision-making during an airway crisis. With regular cricothyrotomy training, anesthesia providers can improve their confidence and adherence to the proper steps required to successfully perform a cricothyrotomy. A Delphi Analysis surveyed anesthesia providers within the Southern California Kaiser Permanente Region. After three Delphi rounds, consensus from anesthesia providers provided the outline for the design of a Cricothyrotomy Education and Training module. This online education and training module can be utilized to provide regular cricothyrotomy training to help maintain anesthesia provider's skills if emergency front of the neck access is needed.

Keywords: Cricothyrotomy, Delphi analysis, front of neck access, anesthesia non-technical skills.

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Background

Anesthesia providers care for a diverse patient population and rely on evidence-based algorithms to guide the appropriate timing of airway interventions in the unexpected, difficult airway (Apfelbaum et al., 2022). The American Society of Anesthesiologists' (ASA) practice guidelines for managing difficult airways recommend emergency invasive airway access when clinicians fail to establish adequate oxygenation and ventilation (Apfelbaum et al., 2022). Clinicians can experience a failed airway when an unexpected difficulty occurs during airway management and cannot mask ventilate, endotracheally intubate, or ventilate using a supraglottic airway device (Apfelbaum et al., 2022). The ASA states that emergency invasive airway access should be performed when anesthesia providers find themselves in a failed airway situation (Apfelbaum et al., 2022). These techniques include surgical cricothyrotomy, needle cricothyrotomy with a pressure-regulating device, large-bore cannula cricothyrotomy, or surgical tracheostomy (Apfelbaum et al., 2022).

Cricothyrotomy is a rarely used, potentially lifesaving procedure that involves accessing the patient's airway surgically or percutaneously via the cricothyroid membrane to facilitate oxygenation and ventilation (Doody & Smart, 2020). Anesthesia providers rarely face a failed airway, as the prevalence within a hospital system can be as low as 2.3 per 1,000 intubation attempts (0.23%) (Kwon et al., 2019). The two most common methods of invasive airway management are surgical cricothyrotomy and needle cricothyrotomy (Pracy et al., 2016). The United Kingdom based Difficult Airway Society's (DAS) current guidelines also recommend invasive means to gain access to a patient's airway in a failed airway; however, the DAS specifically recommends surgical cricothyrotomy as the means to acquire emergency airway access over the other techniques suggested by the ASA (Frerk et al., 2015). Surgical

cricothyrotomy is the fastest and most reliable way to access a patient's airway in a failed airway situation (Price & McCoy, 2019). It also provides long-term access to the patient's airway and is associated with fewer complications than the needle cricothyrotomy with a pressure-regulating device (Frerk et al., 2015). There are many ways to perform a surgical cricothyrotomy; however, the DAS recommends the scalpel-finger-bougie technique because the only materials required for the procedure, a scalpel and gum elastic bougie, are found in most operating rooms (Frerk et al., 2015).

Even when following the ASA or DAS difficult airway algorithm, the decision and intervention of a cricothyrotomy remain challenging. The infrequent use of the surgical cricothyrotomy, reluctance to use the procedure, and the inability of anesthesia providers to identify the cricothyroid membrane are all factors that may put patients at risk and may expose anesthesia providers to civil liability. The consequences of not being able to complete a cricothyrotomy when indicated can significantly contribute to adverse patient outcomes and provider liability (Joffe et al., 2019). The three most common adverse effects of difficult airways are death, brain death, and airway trauma (Joffe et al., 2019). According to the Closed Claims Database Project, which gathers lawsuits from anesthesia providers and insurance providers to improve anesthesia safety, only about 76% of failed airways led to a cricothyrotomy attempt (Joffe et al., 2019). Since cricothyrotomy is the final step in the difficult airway algorithm and the procedure is performed infrequently, the decision to perform a cricothyrotomy may be challenging. The reluctance to commit to a cricothyrotomy is often riskier than the procedure itself (Higgs et al., 2018). Task fixation is a common problem on the path toward cricothyrotomy (Price & McCoy, 2019). According to The Anesthesia Closed Claims Database, anesthesia providers failed to recognize the necessity of a cricothyrotomy. Providers delayed the procedure

in 33% of failed airways, indicating there are human factors that contribute to adverse airway outcomes (Joffe et al., 2019). Furthermore, when performing a cricothyrotomy, many providers are inefficient and struggle to identify anatomical landmarks. Siddiqui et al. (2018) found that providers who used standard manual techniques to determine the cricothyroid membrane were only successful about 8% of the time.

Southern California Kaiser Permanente (KP) does not currently provide regular training for anesthesia providers to practice failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy (S. Kovaian, personal correspondence, September 28, 2022). Given the low frequency of airway emergencies, anesthesia providers cannot rely on clinical practice alone to maintain cricothyrotomy proficiency. Without more frequent educational opportunities, anesthesia provider confidence, competence, and ability to perform a cricothyrotomy will not improve (Hughes et al., 2018; Rajwani et al., 2019). This gap in cricothyrotomy training presents an opportunity for airway experts to come to a consensus on the best cricothyrotomy education material and improve cricothyrotomy training at KP. Designing an online cricothyrotomy training for anesthesia providers at KP can improve provider confidence, efficiency, and knowledge on when to perform a cricothyrotomy (Sun et al., 2017).

Purpose Statement

Using the Iowa Model revised and Delphi method, this project aims to identify cricothyrotomy and failed airway training resources for anesthesia providers within KP, Southern California. Specific aims included a) assessing airway experts' opinions about cricothyrotomy, b) establishing consensus from selected airway experts regarding cricothyrotomy education, and c) using the results from our Delphi study and literature review to create an outline for a cricothyrotomy education and training module.

Review of Literature

Overview

The ever-present risk of the inability to ventilate or intubate in a failed airway situation is dangerous for patients and exposes anesthesia providers to liability (Joffe et al., 2019). Ninety-seven malpractice lawsuits were filed against anesthesia providers due to improper airway management between 2000 and 2012 (Joffe et al., 2019). Only about 37% of emergency airways are appropriately placed during failed airways, and without frequent training, 70% of emergency airways placed are likely to fail (Rosenstock et al., 2016). The ASA, the United Kingdom-based DAS, and the Canadian Airway Focus Group suggest surgical cricothyrotomy to restore ventilation and oxygenation in failed airway situations (Apfelbaum et al., 2022; Frerk et al., 2015; Law et al., 2021). Despite surgical cricothyrotomy being an appropriate way to restore ventilation and oxygenation, many anesthesiologists are not confident in their skill, do not feel it is their role, or do not know when to provide emergency cricothyrotomy (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019). These factors often lead to delays in surgical airway intervention, which can increase patient mortality associated with failed airways (Joffe et al., 2019). This literature review aims to understand the incidence of cricothyrotomy, the training availability for anesthesia providers, and how to improve patient outcomes in failed airway situations.

Literature Search strategy

We conducted a literature review using PubMed, COCHRANE, Google Scholar, and CINAHL Complete electronic databases to collect articles for scholarly review. Articles were limited to articles published in English from 2015 to 2022. Search terms included "cricothyrotomy training," "medical decision making," "non-technical anesthesia skills," and "difficult airway algorithm." Articles were also found using the reference lists of articles found

via database search. Inclusion criteria identified articles in English, peer-reviewed articles, and supplied a high level of evidence. We excluded grey literature and articles greater than eight years since publication. Of note, two papers were selected for inclusion with a publication date older than five years. The first was an extensive systematic review and meta-analysis that furthered our understanding of the incidence of cricothyrotomy. The second article was included due to its unique focus on stressors and their effects on provider adherence to difficult airway algorithms. A total of 17 articles were included in this literature review.

Benefits of Cricothyrotomy Training

High acuity, low occurrence (HALO) procedures can increase provider uncertainty, as anesthesia providers generally do not perform them frequently enough to maintain their skills (Bilic et al., 2020). Fradet et al. (2020) reported only eight percent of anesthesia providers reported confidence in performing a surgical cricothyrotomy. Without frequent airway training, there is a significant decrease in skill performance, adherence to difficult airway algorithms, and medical decision-making (Rosenstock et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2017). Furthermore, this deterioration of skill retention occurs across all airway management types, indicating a need for frequent training to maintain airway skills (Sun et al., 2017; Walshe et al., 2019).

There is a large variety of cricothyrotomy training modalities available for anesthesia providers (Fradet et al., 2020; Hart et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2017). Simple interventions like classroom training and instructional videos can improve anesthesia provider performance (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019). For example, an educational video and cricothyrotomy hands-on workshop improved anesthesia providers' reported confidence level from 8% to 91% (Fradet et al., 2020). Simulation-based education offers a controlled learning environment for failed airway situations and has been shown to improve cricothyrotomy skills and reduce procedure

time (Bilic et al., 2020; Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Rajwani et al., 2019; Rosenstock et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2017). High-fidelity training environments like failed airway simulation on trachea models (tissue or synthetic) attempt to replicate performing a cricothyrotomy on a human patient and have been shown to significantly improve anesthesia provider skill (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Hart et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2021).

Simulation-Based Training

Simulation-based training (SBT) is a popular education style for cricothyrotomy. Research shows SBT significantly improves cricothyrotomy competence, knowledge, and performance in anesthesia providers (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Rajwani et al., 2019; Walshe et al., 2019). The HALO nature of failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy make them ideal for SBT (Bilic et al., 2020; Rajwani et al., 2019). Educators can use high-fidelity trainers to create scenarios that model a failed airway situation with a simulated need for prompt decision-making and cricothyrotomy (Rajwani et al., 2019). Because of this, simulation provides a safe environment for anesthesia providers to hone their surgical skills and establish cricothyrotomy technique preference (Fradet et al., 2020). For example, between the three cricothyrotomy techniques of surgical, percutaneous, and scalpel-bougie-tube, the latter increased the most in provider preference during SBT (Fradet et al., 2020). A systematic review by Walshe et al. (2019) examined 39 articles and found that SBT provided a statistically significant increase in provider situational awareness. SBT reduces delays in arriving at cricothyrotomy in failed airway situations, potentially reducing adverse patient outcomes (Fradet et al., 2020; Kong et al., 2015; Rajwani et al., 2019).

Non-simulation Based Training

Overall, SBT remains the most popular format for failed airway situational training (Sun et al., 2017). Still, there may be advantages to non-simulation-based training (NSBT) (e.g., lectures, videos, clinical observation) (Hart et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2017). A systematic review of 17 articles by Sun et al. (2017) that analyzed the educational effects of NSBT concluded that NSBT produces similar outcomes to SBT in terms of time, skill, success rate of cricothyrotomy, and examination score. A limitation of this finding is that the researchers only selected one study related to surgical cricothyrotomy, suggesting the need for further research (Sun et al., 2017). Combining NSBT and SBT may have improved educational outcomes instead of relying on NSBT alone (Fradet et al., 2020). Research has shown improved confidence, competence, knowledge, skill, and situational awareness related to failed airway and cricothyrotomy when blending NSBT with SBT (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Rajwani et al., 2019). The low cost and ease of use of NSBT may attract some providers to this training method, but SBT remains the better evidence-based method of training when used alone (Walshe et al., 2019).

Available Trainers

Theoretically, the trainer that best resembles the anatomy and tissue of the human neck offers the most realistic cricothyrotomy training. Because of this, training has traditionally included porcine tissue models or human cadaver labs combined with a modality of didactic learning (Hughes et al., 2018). However, new synthetic models from 3D printers, high-fidelity mannequins, homemade trainers, and virtual reality simulators offer a diverse training environment with unique educational opportunities (Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021).

Tissue Models

Tissue models (TM) are high-fidelity trainers that use live, anesthetized animals, cadavers, or post-mortem animal tissue for simulation (Hart et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). Explanted porcine trachea TM are traditionally the standard for cricothyrotomy training, as the anatomy of this trainer very closely resembles the human neck landmarks, tissue, and vasculature (Hart et al., 2017; Jing et al., 2021). While TM offers a high-fidelity learning experience, they have drawbacks. TM are expensive, considered biohazards, have a limited shelf life, and can be vectors for disease (Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). For example, porcine tracheas cost about \$40 per unit (Jing et al., 2021). Current research recommends that cricothyrotomy be performed several times during simulation, but the porcine model is not always practical (Hughes et al., 2018). In addition, TM are not ideal for training multiple anesthesia providers, as they are not durable or reusable (Hughes et al., 2018). Finally, the use of TM is also ethically questionable. Animal rights groups have questioned the use of live animals, and the search for alternative solutions has been undertaken to avoid ethically questionable training (Hart et al., 2017).

Simulated Tissue Models

Simulated tissue models (STM) can include mannequin trainers, 3D-printed tracheas, and synthetic models (Huang et al., 2021). Thus, there is varying fidelity across simulated tissue models (STM) (Huang et al., 2021). High-fidelity STM, like the SimMan mannequin, are associated with high costs and have inferior simulation outcomes compared to lower-fidelity STM at improving cricothyrotomy performance and comfort with the procedure (Massoth et al., 2019). New STM have improved anatomy landmarks, tissue fidelity, and the capability of bleeding to provide a high-quality simulation environment for learning (Hughes et al., 2018).

Thus, if designed appropriately, STM can reliably improve cricothyrotomy skills, reduce procedure time, improve skill retention, and improve cricothyrotomy confidence (Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). Studies show that 3D-printed models are non-inferior to LT trainers and are easily modified to bleed to increase fidelity (Hughes et al., 2018; Huang et al., 2021; Jing et al., 2021). 3D-printed cricothyrotomy trainers are ideal as 3D-printed tracheas are cheap, durable, and reusable (Hughes et al., 2018). The cost for a single, reusable 3D-printed trachea is \$7 USD, and a higher fidelity bleeding tissue pad is \$6 USD per use (Hughes et al., 2018). A recent crossover study by Jing et al. (2021) cited saving \$650 by using 3D-printed trainers instead of LT models. The reusability, ability to increase fidelity with simulated bleeding, low cost, and ability to improve the perception of performance and actual performance make 3D-printed tracheas the ideal training material for failed airway and cricothyrotomy SBT.

Barriers to Increasing Cricothyrotomy Training

While the literature clearly shows SBT for failed airway and cricothyrotomy training is beneficial for both patients and providers, getting employers to buy into a training program may hinder the implementation of new SBT-based training. With a prevalence of 0.23%, cricothyrotomy's HALO status could make it difficult for employers or educators to see cricothyrotomy education and simulation as urgent (Kwon et al., 2019). The cost of implementing such a program could be a barrier to implementation. The cost of STM can range from \$7 USD per unit to thousands of dollars for a high-fidelity sim mannequin (Hughes et al., 2018). In addition to the cost of STM, employers will also incur the cost of scalpels, flexible bougie stylets, and labor for simulation employees and trainees. Training should be repeated

frequently to be effective (Rajwani et al., 2019); thus, the cost of a failed airway and cricothyrotomy education and simulation program will not be temporary.

Another disincentive for employers to prioritize cricothyrotomy education is the inability to tie simulation success to real-world success. While the evidence is clear that providers feel more competent, confident, knowledgeable, and improve performance within a simulation, further research is needed to support that ability to perform in simulation translates to an ability to perform when a cricothyrotomy is needed clinically (Rajwani et al., 2019). The research articles included in this review come from a diverse background of airway professionals but determining educational needs between the professions is difficult. Cricothyrotomy research has been conducted by student nurse anesthetists, military personnel, combat paramedics, and ENT Specialists, but there is not a current study that provides a consensus among the professions to standardized cricothyrotomy training for best patient outcomes (Groom et al., 2019; Hart et al., 2017).

Non-Technical Behavior Training

Research identifies the need for excellent anesthesia non-technical skills (ANTS) for providers to efficiently manage a failed airway crisis as a team leader (Ambardekar et al., 2019; Fradet et al., 2020). Without non-technical skills like task management, teamwork, situational awareness, and medical decision-making, appropriate airway interventions may be delayed (Fradet et al., 2020; Helou et al., 2020; Krage et al., 2017). Traditionally, researchers have utilized the anesthesia non-technical skills (ANTS) scoring system to score non-technical skills within the training environment (Krage et al., 2017). This scoring system was explicitly designed for anesthesia providers and helps analyze the providers' ability to use ANTS to make potentially lifesaving decisions within a failed airway scenario (Helou et al., 2020; Kong et al., 2015; Krage

et al., 2017). Thus, there is a strong correlation between ANTS scoring and the team leader's ability to manage an airway crisis (Krage et al., 2017). A crossover study performed by Krage et al. (2017) showed that ANTS scores decreased by an average of 2.0 points when external pressures were added to simulation training.

There is no consistent emphasis on non-technical behaviors with cricothyrotomy and difficult airway training for anesthesia providers (Kong et al., 2015; Walshe et al., 2019). While simulation-based education seems to correlate with improved ANTS scores, anesthesia providers are more likely to receive team leadership training during advanced life support courses (ACLS) compared to airway courses (Krage et al., 2017; Walshe et al., 2019). After receiving non-technical skills training during SBT, participants report a positive impact on medical decision-making (Jersby et al., 2017). Thus, advanced airway providers are more likely to benefit from domain-specific, simulated stressor training (Walshe et al., 2019). Research shows increased ANTS scores with simulation-based crisis training, but further research is needed to define skill transfer and duration of improved non-technical behavior (Jersby et al., 2017; Walshe et al., 2019).

Medical-Decision Making during Crisis

Further research is needed to understand the correlation between non-technical behavior and medical decision-making. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis highlighted uncertainty as the central theme affecting medical decision-making and emphasized using algorithm tools to guide providers to a decision point (Helou et al., 2020; Walsh et al., 2019). Helou et al. (2020) identifies four main subthemes for education when guiding providers navigating uncertainty: intuition, protocol-driven decision, or team-based problem-solving strategies. Because of this, anesthesia providers are instructed to rely on difficult airway

algorithms for rapid, protocol-driven decision-making during failed airway situations (Kong et al., 2015; Helou et al., 2020). Reliance on a difficult airway algorithm decreases external stressors and eases the team leader's cognitive load (Ambardekar et al., 2019).

Difficult airway algorithms should be straightforward and simple to improve anesthesia providers' recall during a crisis (Ambardekar et al., 2019; Kong et al., 2015). While the ASA's difficult airway algorithm (DAA) is traditionally taught in the U.S., the DAS Vortex Approach is becoming popular due to its simplicity and decreased provider cognitive load (Ambardekar et al., 2019). Anesthesia providers improve adherence to airway algorithms and decision-making after simulated failed airway training (Ambardekar et al., 2019; Walshe et al., 2019). Using an algorithm may reduce cognitive load, but it does not necessarily translate into better teamwork, improved situational awareness, and ANTS (Kong et al., 2015). While there seems to be a correlation between the increased performance of non-technical skills with decreased cognitive load, more research is needed (Guris et al., 2021). Until more research is available, cricothyrotomy simulation training incorporating non-technical anesthesia skills like situational awareness and leadership will best prepare anesthesia providers for the rare, failed airway situation.

Summary of Review of Literature

The literature review clearly shows that failed airway situations and cricothyrotomies are an area of anesthesia practice where providers lack knowledge, experience, and training (Apfelbaum et al., 2022; Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Rajwani et al., 2019). Considering failed airway situations' negative impact when providers are not adequately trained, frequent education surrounding failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy should be implemented to improve difficult airway management. The literature outlines a need for

standardized training to improve anesthesia providers' confidence, competence, knowledge, and skill surrounding failed airway and the cricothyrotomy procedure. Current research supports using simulation-based training, but identifies educational value in lectures, videos, and observation, to improve outcomes with failed airway and cricothyrotomy (Sun et al., 2017). Cheap, reusable SMT are just as efficient at improving provider confidence, competence, knowledge, and skill compared to more expensive, single-use live tissue trainers (Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). More research is needed to determine how simulation training best improves ANTS related specifically to cricothyrotomy (Kong et al., 2015; Walshe et al., 2019). Finally, more research is needed to specifically identify the educational needs of the anesthesia provider. Various professionals conduct cricothyrotomy SBT, but there is yet to be a consensus among the professions on what cricothyrotomy training should include (Hart et al., 2017).

KP vision is to be a leader in total health by making lives better (KP, 2018). KP states that they aim to create a safe patient environment by making patient safety every patient's right and every employee's responsibility (KP, 2018). KP's intention to achieve its vision by improving patient safety provides evidence that there will be organizational support for educational programs that seek to improve patient safety. This project aims to strengthen anesthesia providers' training resources, improve outcomes related to failed airway situations, and increase the confidence of anesthesia providers within KP Southern California in performing surgical cricothyrotomy. We intend to accomplish these goals by gathering expert consensus as to the best type of failed airway and cricothyrotomy education. After achieving expert consensus, we will design an online educational cricothyrotomy module for the continuing education of anesthesia providers at KP.

Supporting Frameworks

Background

Clinicians use a variety of frameworks to guide the implementation of evidence-based practice (EBP). Selecting a framework that matches the project's aims is essential for successful EBP change (Cullen, 2018). One such framework is The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care. The Iowa Model was developed in the 1990s by nurses at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (UIHC) and has been used worldwide as a practical, application-oriented guide for EBP implementation ever since (Bulkwalter et al., 2017). The original Iowa Model was based on Rodger's (1983) Theory of Diffusions and Innovations and stemmed from the Quality Assurance Model Using Research (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The original model has been revised multiple times to accommodate healthcare changes, incorporate various evidence levels, and provide further guidance about implementing change (Cullen, 2018). The Iowa Model is a problem-solving approach that aims to organize the process of implementing EBP (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Because of this, the Iowa Model is intended for clinicians seeking systematic change and implementation of EBP (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Revised Iowa Model was selected as the framework for this project for its practicality and current use across KP Southern California (KP, 2022).

In addition to the Iowa Model framework, the Delphi Technique (DT) was also selected to guide our approach through the applicable Iowa Model steps for this project. The DT was first developed in the 1960s by Norman Dalkey and Olaf Helmer to gain expert consensus on topics for the defense industry (Barrett & Heale, 2020). Since then, the framework has evolved and

been adopted by other research areas, including Nursing (Barrett & Heale, 2020). The DT is known for its flexible approach to gathering expert consensus on a topic (Barret & Heale, 2020).

Model Concepts

The Iowa Model is a theoretical framework that utilizes a flow chart to provide clear, concise steps to guide clinicians in applying an evidence-based change in practice from clinical and systems perspectives (Cullen, 2018). This framework helps identify the initial problem and the appropriate interventions necessary to sustain practice after implementing a change (Cullen, 2018). The Revised Iowa Model provides direction on how to proceed for each step along the flow chart to facilitate the change process (Chiwaula et al., 2021).

The Revised Iowa Model suggests EBP begins with identifying "triggers," or practice issues, challenges, or desired changes in outcomes (Cullen, 2018). These triggers may arise from new knowledge or clinical problem identification (Cullen, 2018). The next step in The Revised Iowa Model is to convert an identified trigger into a PICO (P= patient/population/problem, I= intervention, C= comparison, O= outcome) question (Cullen, 2018). The third step is to determine whether the trigger (or change) is essential enough to be addressed by an EBP project. The Iowa Model guides this determination by reminding the investigator that EBP projects that address issues with high volume, high risk, high cost or that align with institutional goals are typically considered high priority and warrant change (Cullen, 2018). After committing to an issue, a team of invested individuals with the proper skills and organizational ties is formed to implement EBP (Cullen, 2018). Next, the team conducts a complete review of the literature published on the selected topic. Team members then synthesize the literature review to determine if there is enough evidence to suggest that a change in practice is justified (Cullen, 2018). Should there be insufficient evidence, the Revised Iowa Model suggests circling back to collect more

information before continuing (Cullen, 2018). If published literature suggests an EBP project is reasonable, the team should design EBP guidelines and develop a pilot study to validate published evidence in a clinical setting (Cullen, 2018). The team should then evaluate the results of the pilot study, and practice guidelines should be assessed based on the pilot data (Cullen, 2018). If the pilot study indicates the change is appropriate, it should be integrated and sustained in practice (Cullen, 2018). Finally, the project results should be disseminated (Cullen, 2018). See Appendix A for a flowchart of The Revised Iowa Model.

While the Iowa Model is straightforward and prescriptive, the DT is much broader. DT is the method of choice when little is known about a topic or when there would be a benefit of gathering expert consensus on a problem (Vernon, 2009). The DT starts with identifying an area of interest, followed by developing a question. The DT is based on multiple rounds of questions where experts in a particular field are asked about their opinion (Barrett & Heale, 2020). Researchers establish criteria for experts in a particular area and invite those who meet the requirements to participate in the expert panel (Vernon, 2009). Experts can be homogenous or heterogeneous. When investigators seek consensus on a highly technical issue, the experts should be homogenous; however, when gathering consensus on a broad subject, a heterogenous expert pool may benefit from a more comprehensive understanding of the area. Researchers should prepare a list of potential experts and recruitment strategies (Vernon, 2009). After experts have been recruited, round one can begin. Typically, round one contains a survey with open-ended questions to cast a wide net of possible responses (Vernon, 2009). Reactions to the first round are then considered, collated, and analyzed. Responses are then redistributed to experts for further reflection. Delphi rounds continue until the desired level of consensus is reached (Vernon, 2009). Each round of questions is based on the previous round, allowing the study's focus to evolve with

findings over time (Barrett & Heale, 2020). Participants are allowed to see and reflect on the previous rounds' responses, intended to allow each respondent to reflect on other expert views and respond directly to the strengths and weaknesses of different specialist opinions (Barrett & Heale, 2020). When opinions are shared with other experts, they are always shared anonymously to prevent bias and avoid concern for negative feedback for their personal views (Barrett & Heale, 2020). Researchers determine what consensus is, how to operationalize the respondents' opinions, and choose how many rounds of questions are sufficient (Barrett & Heale, 2020). See Appendix B for a flowchart explaining the Delphi technique.

Models in the Literature

Literature Using the Iowa Model

The Iowa Model is among the most renowned frameworks for implementing EBP due to its ease of use and applicability to healthcare (Chiwaula et al., 2021). Quality improvement (QI) teams from across the world and from multiple aspects of healthcare choose the Iowa Model to implement EBP due to its problem-solving approach, focus on the implementation of EBP, and clarity at each step (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Chiwaula et al., 2021).

Fannon et al. (2020) used the Iowa Model in a QI project to create and implement a protocol for safely administering dexmedetomidine for deep procedural sedation in non-intubated patients. This QI Project identified the respiratory depression frequently experienced during deep sedation cases as the triggering issue for a change. The new protocol defined roles for nurses and physicians, set monitoring standards, and required that all nurses caring for patients maintain Pediatric Advanced Life Support. Fannon et al. (2020) created a training program to educate nurses on the new protocols for dexmedetomidine and conducted pre-post-education surveys, competency exams, and selected educational tools for continuing the protocol

implementation. Based on survey feedback, the project adjusted educational tools to sustain new protocol implementation by identifying possible gaps in education. Overall, the QI project improved knowledge and protocol implementation of safe dexmedetomidine use in deep sedation of pediatric patients (Fannon et al., 2020).

A QI project by Jannotta et al. (2021) identified central venous catheter (CVC) complications as triggers to implement an evidence-based protocol to administer 3% sodium chloride through alternative routes like peripheral lines. 3% sodium chloride has historically only been administered through central lines for fear of vascular injury due to the hypertonic nature of the solution (Jannotta et al., 2021). However, there is an increased risk and decreased benefit with CVC use for 3% sodium chloride administration, as arterial puncture, sepsis, and pneumothorax risks increase. The group used the Iowa Model to develop a standardized approach to train a multidisciplinary team on their new protocol (Jannotta et al., 2021). The standardized approach of the Iowa Model led to a successful practice change with few adverse events and reduced the number of CVCs placed in patients during implementation (Jannotta et al. 2021).

A third study by Servas et al. (2022) utilized the Iowa Model to develop a standardized perioperative handoff report between anesthesia providers and registered nurses (RNs) in the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU). Servas et al. (2022) identified that crucial information was lost during handoffs between anesthesia providers and PACU registered nurses, leading to increased sentinel hospital events and patient mortality. After conducting a literature review and assembling a QI team, Servas et al. (2022) implemented a PACU pause, which allowed the nurse to settle the patient before the handoff of patient care was started. Audit tools and post-intervention surveys were utilized to evaluate the efficacy of the new protocol and adjust to

sustain the new protocol implementation. Their standardized handoff tool prevented miscommunication and improved patient safety in their hospital's PACU (Servas et al., 2022).

Literature using DT

While the Delphi technique is used by many, it differs from the Iowa model in that it is broad and open to interpretation, which leads to variations in the number of rounds, question delivery, and how consensus is judged by researchers utilizing the model (Barrett & Heale 2020). One study by Roth et al. (2017) aimed to gather expert consensus on human factors contributing to human causes of nursing errors. Roth et al. (2017) selected Nurse experts from two hospital systems and used only two rounds. The first round asked 25 experts to list every human cause of medication errors they could identify through open-ended questions. The results of this qualitative survey were synthesized into a Likert-based scale of themes. The list was then returned to the experts, who were asked to rank each factor in order of importance for the second round. Roth et al. (2017) found that fatigue, heavy workload, and communication problems were the top three human reasons for medication errors.

Another study by Heale et al. (2018) recruited nurse practitioners (NPs) to gather consensus about NP advance care planning competencies, as many patients do not have advanced care plans (or end-of-life decision plans). Heale et al. (2018) designed three rounds of questionnaires for NP experts. The first-round competencies were developed using findings from a survey based on NP beliefs surrounding advanced care planning. The second round engaged 29 NPs who evaluated the draft competencies. From there, the investigators used the feedback from the second round to revise the competencies, which were then sent back to the NPs for the final round. The final round resulted in 15 of the original 29 NPs reaching a consensus with the final document (Heale et al., 2018). The final document identified four competencies to recruit NP's

awareness of advanced care planning and increase patients' ability to make educated end-of-life decisions.

Iowa Model Steps

Identifying Triggering Issues

The first step of the Iowa Model is identifying a clinical issue (Cullen, 2018). Clinicians can identify a clinical problem in many ways, including by looking at data or the organization's philosophy of care (Cullen, 2018). This project's triggering issue, insufficient cricothyrotomy education for failed airway situations, fits within KP's vision for safe patient care (KP, 2018). The project is also supported by evidence that cricothyrotomy training improves provider confidence, competence, knowledge, and skill in failed airway situations (Rajwani et al., 2019; KP, 2018). Currently, there is no standardized cricothyrotomy training for anesthesia providers at KP in Southern California to maintain their skills.

State the Question or Purpose

The Iowa Model suggests using a PICO statement to focus a broad need for clinical information to a more focused question to articulate a purpose statement and to use as a guide when looking for evidence to support an EBP change (Cullen, 2018). This evidence-based QI project aims to improve provider confidence with failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy at KP Southern California by designing an online cricothyrotomy education and training module and creating a synthetic training model for a hands-on demonstration.

Is the Topic a Priority?

Providing safe patient care is a priority for KP, as evidenced by the organization's vision (KP, 2018). As our literature review suggests, failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy procedures expose patients to significant risks for adverse outcomes. Provider well-being can

also suffer due to these critical situations depending on the outcome (Joffe et al., 2019; Rajwani et al., 2019). Research has shown that the use of non-simulation-based training (NSBT) and simulation-based training (SBT) improves provider comfort with failed airway situations and cricothyrotomy (Hart et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2017). Therefore, our QI project intends to assist KP in its vision of providing the safest care possible.

Form a Team

A multidisciplinary team is essential in the Iowa Model framework (Cullen, 2018). We have formed an initial group to launch our project to address the lack of education provided to anesthesia providers surrounding failed airways and cricothyrotomy. Dr. Jeremy Heiner is the team leader for this project. Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) Doctor of Nursing Practice students Jessica Godshall and Jake Moss conducted a literature review and will develop an educational plan related to failed airway and cricothyrotomy for KP Southern California. Dr. Hannah Fraley is our project's adviser at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). Other stakeholders for our project include Dr. Mark Gabot and KP executives.

Gather and Analyze Evidence

A literature review was conducted using PubMed, COCHRANE, Google Scholar, and CINAHL Complete electronic databases to collect scholarly evidence to support the need for failed airway and cricothyrotomy education and determine acceptable training methods. We searched the databases using the terms "cricothyrotomy training," "medical decision making," "non-technical anesthesia skills," and "difficult airway algorithm" to look for peer-reviewed journal articles that supplied high levels of evidence written in English. We also examined KP's website to determine if this project would garner organizational support. KP's website indicated

they would support our project as their vision is to provide the safest patient care possible and improve patient safety (KP, 2018).

Our comprehensive literature review identified 17 articles that supported non-simulation-based training (NSBT) and simulation-based training (SBT) to improve provider confidence during failed airway and cricothyrotomy. Simple NSBT improves outcomes related to failed airway and cricothyrotomy, especially when combined with SBT (Sun et al., 2017). Use of traditional tissue models or relatively cheap, synthetic tissue models to practice cricothyrotomy techniques improved provider confidence, competence, knowledge, and skill surrounding failed airway and the cricothyrotomy procedure (Fradet et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). However, neither NSBT nor SBT had evidence to support an improvement in anesthesia non-technical skills (ANTS), which are imperative to successfully implement the cricothyrotomy procedure in failed airway scenarios (Kong et al., 2015; Walshe et al., 2019).

Is there Sufficient Evidence?

Evidence suggests NSBT and SBT improve provider confidence, competence, knowledge, and skill related to failed airway scenarios and cricothyrotomy (Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et al., 2021). Research conducted by a variety of airway experts, such as military combat medics, anesthesiologists, head and neck surgeons, certified nurse anesthetists, emergency medicine physicians, and acute care physicians, demonstrated the need for regular cricothyrotomy training (Fradet et al., 2020; Groom et al., 2019; Hart et al., 2017). However, there is no expert consensus on the best training method available in the current literature. The lack of expert consensus represents a significant gap. Therefore, our project will

use the DT to gather consensus from various airway experts on best practices for realistic failed airway scenarios and cricothyrotomy training programs.

Methods

Due to the infrequent nature of cricothyrotomy, evidence suggests that regular education and training is required to establish and maintain anesthesia providers' cricothyrotomy skills (Sun et al., 2017; Walshe et al., 2019). The literature review did not present a superior type of cricothyrotomy education across a diverse population of airway experts. Due to the lack of expert consensus for the best method to standardize cricothyrotomy training, we used the Delphi technique to survey airway experts to establish expert consensus on the most appropriate cricothyrotomy training technique.

Design

Using the Iowa Model as a framework, this Quality Improvement (QI) project used Delphi methodology to establish expert consensus regarding the best training technique for cricothyrotomy.

Team

The team consisted of two Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) graduate students serving as team leads, Jessica Godshall and Jake Moss, one KPSA faculty member, Dr. Jeremy Heiner, and one California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) advisor, Dr. Hannah Fraley. The DNP project team members recruited airway experts for inclusion in the Delphi study, determined ongoing survey questions, decided on the number of survey rounds needed based on responses, and established a level of consensus appropriate for the completion of the Delphi study. The KP IRB and the CSUF IRB approved this project.

Participants

A consensus is best reached with a homozygous expert pool when dealing with highly technical issues like cricothyrotomy (Vernon, 2009). Most studies that utilize the Delphi

technique select experts based on institutional affiliation (Niederberger & Spranger, 2020). Therefore, we established a purposive sample of potential panel members who are "airway experts." Purposive sampling is used when researchers look to include categories of people, such as airway experts, in a study (Grove & Gray, 2019). The team defined airway experts as those who have been educated on the anatomy and physiology of the human airway (i.e., nasopharynx, oropharynx, laryngopharynx, trachea, lungs) and routinely access the airway as a part of their profession. Potential panel members consisted of any airway expert who wished to participate. Next, we emailed potential participants an invitation to participate in the first Delphi round of the survey. All participant information remained confidential. According to a systematic review by Niederberger and Spranger (2020), most research utilizing the Delphi technique has between 10 and 100 participants, with a median of 17 experts. Therefore, we aimed to have about 17 respondents on our panel of experts. However, if we have fewer respondents than that, many studies have reached a consensus with less than ten experts in their panel, and our study would still be able to establish expert consensus (Nasa et al., 2021).

Ethical Considerations

Data from the Delphi study will be collected directly from non-patient volunteers via email. No patient data will be included in our survey questions or responses. Survey responses will be deidentified to maintain respondent anonymity. Completed surveys with respondent identifiers will be stored in a password-protected folder in a password-protected excel document, password-protected computer, and 256-bit encryption by Apple FileVault. Before implementation, our proposal was deemed exempt for review by both the KP Southern California Institutional Review Board (IRB) and the California State University, Fullerton IRB. The

exemptions can be found in appendix G. The exemptions indicate that our project posed little to no risk to human participants.

Data Collection

The Delphi technique guides a group of experts to reach a consensus of concepts and opinions utilizing several rounds of questions, each of which builds upon the responses of a previous round of questions (Niederberger & Spranger, 2020). The Delphi method usually consists of two to three rounds of questioning until the predetermined level of consensus has been met (Niederberger & Spranger, 2020).

Delphi Rounds

Both qualitative and quantitative survey data was obtained during each Delphi round. Open-ended questions comprised the qualitative component to discover themes among experts' responses. Quantitative data was collected using Likert scales. The typical underlying constructs of Likert scales targeted the measurement of agreement, perceptions, attitudes, or beliefs of those surveyed (Grove & Gray, 2019). Response choices in Likert scales addressed agreement, evaluation, or frequency (Grove & Gray, 2019). Agreement choices ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree, frequency choices were usually never, frequently, sometimes, all the time, and evaluation scales are usually rated from poor to excellent (Grove & Gray, 2019). Likert scales with an even number of responses represented forced choice scales and prohibited respondents from providing a neutral, middle response that would be available if an odd number of choices are given in a survey (Grove & Gray, 2019). The team developed an initial set of questions operationalizing the constructs to understand the participants' levels of agreement with the items using a forced choice Likert scale.

The first Delphi round consisted of open-ended and forced-choice Likert scale questions regarding cricothyrotomy training. See Appendix D for the survey sent for the first round of questioning. Questions were chosen to allow experts to reflect on their experiences related to cricothyrotomy and enable them to identify what they thought was important in cricothyrotomy training. Deidentified responses from the first round of qualitative responses were sent to the experts for reflection, along with the second round of survey questions that were developed based on themes identified by the first round of questioning. Responses were collected and collated within a password-protected excel file on a 256-bit encrypted, password-protected computer. The process was repeated for a third round. After responses to each round are complete, operationalization and synthesis of responses occur. The Delphi technique does not have a required level of consensus as part of the framework, but researchers determine the degree of consensus. According to Niederberger and Spranger (2020), most research utilizing the Delphi technique established expert consensus as 60% agreement between experts. Therefore, we will set a consensus of 60% agreement between experts on cricothyrotomy themes and strategies.

Methods of Evaluation

Currently there is no standardized tool to evaluate the quality of Delphi Studies (Jünger et al., 2017; Nasa et al., 2021). Our team selected a nine-step tool by Nasa et al. (2021) designed to guide the evaluation of Delphi Studies in healthcare. The tool listed in Appendix D provides nine evaluation points in a four-step methodological process to conduct the evaluation of Delphi studies (Nasa et al., 2021). First, the team defined the problem area and documented the research process. The literature review documented the databases utilized, inclusion criteria, variables, search terms, and keywords. Next, panel members were evaluated according to predetermined standards and panel members were evaluated as their expertise relates to the problem statement.

Each Delphi round evaluated evolving discussions and themes based on previous Delphi rounds while maintaining panelists' anonymity. Delphi rounds were complete when the project's closing criteria were met. Closing criteria required a 60% level of consensus, with or without stability in survey results. Stability is defined by Nasa et al. (2021) as the consistency of responses between successive rounds of a study. Our goal was to achieve stability of results with each Delphi round, but this is not a predetermined requirement to close the study. As illustrated in Appendix E we evaluated stability and consensus following each survey and determined if survey questions needed to be rephrased or removed as the study progressed (Nasa et al., 2021).

The team organized qualitative and quantitative data for analysis after all Delphi rounds were completed. Qualitative data from open-ended questions were analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods, such as content analysis and pie charts (Sandelowski, 2000). Qualitative data was grouped by themes and studied for consensus. Quantitative data from Likert-style questions was de-identified and downloaded from the survey software to Qualtrics for analysis. Quantitative data will be presented in bar charts.

Results

Delphi Analysis

Nineteen participants completed the first survey of the Delphi round. Quantitative results were organized in bar charts using Qualtrics (Appendix H). Frequently mentioned phrases were identified as themes and displayed in a pie chart (Appendix I). Five out of nineteen responses felt “well prepared” for performing cricothyrotomy. These five individuals had recent training (6 months – 1 year) with hands on training (simulation, 3D printer, pig trachea). Remaining responses marked “poorly prepared” with no recent training. One participant marked receiving training only during school. Poorly prepared anesthesia providers were associated with low frequency training, non-simulation-based training, and feeling high levels of stress. Well prepared anesthesia providers were associated with regular cricothyrotomy training and hands-on, simulation-based training (Appendix H).

Results from the first survey guided the creation of a second survey. The second survey was designed to identify potential barriers to current cricothyrotomy training available for anesthesia providers. The thirteen responses received in the second survey were quantified into bar charts using Qualtrics (Appendix J). Eleven out of thirteen responses listed that they did not currently receive annual cricothyrotomy training. One hundred percent of participants that took the second survey marked an interest in receiving annual cricothyrotomy training (Appendix J).

Four participants joined a zoom meeting for the third survey. Four CRNAs were present for the full meeting. Participants agreed on the selected themes identified in the first Delphi Survey (Appendix H). Consensus of one hundred percent of participants agreed that hands-on simulation (SBT) was the most beneficial form of cricothyrotomy training, which was a major theme in this project’s review of the literature. All participants agreed that hands-on simulation

was most valuable as it trained tactile memory and increased familiarity with airway equipment. From the data collected in previous Delphi Rounds, discussion questions were selected to guide the creation of an outline for a cricothyrotomy education and training module (Appendix K). All participants insisted on the importance of including a variety of front of neck access procedure education (surgical, needle, retrograde) as anesthesia providers work in diverse settings with variable equipment available and sometimes specialized patient populations. Barriers to receiving cricothyrotomy training were identified by participants: scheduling, time constraints, and limited resources (pig tracheas). All participants agreed with one hundred percent consensus that the training and education module should be online and offered with accompanying continuing education credits for anesthesia providers. While hands-on, simulation-based cricothyrotomy training may be superior, it is not always convenient for anesthesia providers to access.

Educational Module Outline

After completion of three Delphi rounds, expert consensus guided the creation of an Educational and Training module outline. The education and training module will begin with an overview, followed by an introduction to the training topic of cricothyrotomy. The purpose and objectives of the module will be described, followed by a review of the background of cricothyrotomy. There will be a brief review of cricothyrotomy literature, difficult airway algorithms, the medical decision-making process, and the need for regular cricothyrotomy training to maintain anesthesia provider skill. The module will then teach the cricothyrotomy procedure, including methods for bougie-assisted surgical cricothyrotomy, wire-guided cricothyrotomy, needle cricothyrotomy, and trans-tracheal jet ventilation. Complications and

potential variables that could be encountered will then be discussed. The full outline of the educational and training module can be found in Appendix L.

Discussion

This study used a combination of the Iowa Framework Model and the Delphi technique to create an education and training module outline that combined the best available evidence with expert insight. The Iowa Model's blueprint guided the review of the evidence surrounding effective implementation of a cricothyrotomy education and training module. Delphi Analysis aided with the blending of recent literature and expert consensus regarding the best methods of teaching cricothyrotomy techniques. Since failed airways are possible in all types of populations and practice settings, our project aimed to sample a diverse anesthesia population and consider practice variables.

Of the participants that completed the second survey, 92% reported that they desired education on all cricothyrotomy techniques. Special attention was given to ensuring that the content included in the online module would teach a variety of cricothyrotomy techniques that could be applicable in different practice settings. For example, a pediatric anesthesia provider will need to learn needle cricothyrotomy, but an anesthesia provider working outside the team model might prefer to learn bougie-assisted cricothyrotomy. Concern was voiced during the Delphi Study's second and third round regarding the variability in anesthesia equipment, practice setting, and team model when performing a cricothyrotomy (Appendix J). This confirms our research, as cricothyrotomy training on all techniques (surgical, needle, bougie-assisted) decreases procedural time and provider bias (Fradet et al., 2020; Song et al., 2023). While anesthesia providers will inadeptly develop a preference for one specific cricothyrotomy technique, the online module will equip them to make an informed decision based on their work environment and the needs of the patient (Appendix L). By considering different work

environment variables, the online module will alert anesthesia providers on how to best prepare for a cricothyrotomy before the day it is emergently required (Appendix L).

Feedback from participants during the third Delphi round determined the need for an online, didactic portion of training with hands-on simulation training. Availability was mentioned by all participants as a significant barrier to anesthesia providers seeking cricothyrotomy training. This included busy work hours, decreased free time, and decreased availability of cricothyrotomy classes that fit the participants' schedule. Despite barrier concerns, 100% of second survey participants reported interest in attending an in-person simulation-based cricothyrotomy training session. All participants agreed that online-based training using an educational module would be the best, immediate solution. While our literature review outlines the importance of online training paired with in-person simulation, the reality is that anesthesia providers will not always be available to attend in-person events (Fradet et al., 2020; Kong et al., 2015; Rajwani et al., 2019). Research shows that In-person, simulation-based training best recreates the stress of making the decision to perform a cricothyrotomy, and offers hands-on, tactile learning (Rajwani et al., 2019). Further research is needed to determine how to best offer simulation-based training to anesthesia providers.

Since there is a barrier to in-person class attendance, further research is needed to evaluate new tools available to enhance online learning. New studies have been incorporating the use of virtual reality into critical care training and medical decision making (Chang et al., 2021). With the use of virtual reality, online training can create a stressful situation for learners that mimics the need for quick, assertive medical decision making that is required for cricothyrotomy (Chang et al., 2021). The availability of new, 3D printed tracheas are another exciting tool that participants can use to enhance online education (Huang et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Jing et

al., 2021). This resource was discussed with the participants of the Third Survey with mixed results. One of the participants commented that he had utilized a 3D printer for cricothyrotomy training, while the other three participants had not. Affordable, 3D trachea kits for home practice are a possible solution to increase the availability of hands-on training options (Hughes et al., 2018).

Another concern for our study was measuring the effectiveness of our online education and training module. Recent RCT's have utilized Likert scale style survey questions to quantify the improvement in provider confidence, medical knowledge, and anesthesia non-technical skills in cricothyrotomy training (Fradet et al., 2020; Song et al., 2023). In a study by Song et al., (2023), participants were requested to complete surveys pre-intervention and post-intervention. If low confidence scores are received, research shows the need for improvement and modification of the education intervention (Song et al., 2023). In a different study, Fradet et al. (2020) found that 60-80% of most participants were neutral on the quality of the educational intervention, regardless of improved provider confidence scores. To accurately measure the provider's improvement after completing the online educational and training module, we recommend that individuals complete a pre-intervention and post-intervention survey. Specific questions will guide further versions and modification of the cricothyrotomy module.

Likert scales will also be helpful in the potential creation of an in-person, simulation-based training class. Song et al. (2023) not only used surveys to measure medical knowledge of the cricothyrotomy procedure, but also utilized surveys to guide implementation of simulation-based training. Post-intervention surveys taken by Song et al. (2023) showed improvement in cricothyrotomy performance times, decreased provider bias towards a specific cricothyrotomy technique, and emphasized the importance of sequential performance of cricothyrotomy. Thus,

we recommend pre-intervention and post-intervention surveys be utilized to evaluate quality of online education and in-person simulation efficacy.

Recommendations

A cricothyrotomy education and training module should be created by a future DNP team using the outline in Appendix J. The didactic portion of the educational module will be a voice-over slide show containing important information related to cricothyrotomy and will contain knowledge checks at the end of each section that must be passed before proceeding to the next section. The demonstration portion of the education and training module will contain anesthesia non-technical skills, technical skills, and proper use of equipment detailed in the didactic portion of the module. When the module is completed, it will be reviewed by the KPSA faculty, Delphi participants, and Dr. Jeremy Heiner. The next DNP team should create a pre-intervention and post-intervention survey to determine the effectiveness of the training module. The module should be initially piloted at a Southern California medical facility. Should the pilot pre-intervention and post-intervention survey show that there is an improvement in cricothyrotomy knowledge, confidence, competence, and skill, the group will film and edit multiple videos for wider dissemination of the education and training module. Should the pre-intervention and post-intervention survey indicate no change in cricothyrotomy understanding, adjustments should be made to the module.

Implications

The Delphi analysis demonstrated the importance of annual cricothyrotomy training to improve provider confidence when performing a cricothyrotomy. While all the airway experts in the study agreed there should be annual cricothyrotomy training, the majority had not received training in over one year. The Delphi analysis also indicated that the most significant barrier to

frequent cricothyrotomy education in the cost that would be associated with performing annual simulations. While experts agreed an in person multidisciplinary simulation would be best suited to improve cricothyrotomy skill, it was seen by many to be infeasible due to staffing issues and cost. To remedy this, the Delphi analysis determined an educational module that could be performed completely online would be most ideal.

Limitations

Attrition was a limitation to the study. Only 48% of round one participants took part in the round two survey. The final Zoom Meeting, which was arguably the most important, only had four airway experts in attendance due to a combination of factors. The meeting was held mid-day as it was the only time all DNP group members were able to meet, which made it difficult for airway experts to join. Many of our participants cited work, childcare, decreased availability, or lack of interest in joining the zoom meeting.

Another limitation with our study was the lack of diversity in our survey. We defined airway experts as anyone who regularly accesses the airway for their profession, which in addition to anesthesia providers would have included head and neck surgeons, paramedics, and many other professions; however, we were only able to recruit CRNA's. Unintended bias may have been present in our study as we used convenience sampling and failed to gather demographic data.

Conclusion

The Delphi analysis created an outline for an online educational module based on expert consensus that determined the most important components of cricothyrotomy training for anesthesia providers. Both current literature and expert consensus indicate that cricothyrotomy education and training should be low cost, accessible, and frequent. Both also highlight the

importance of maintaining cricothyrotomy knowledge, confidence, competence, and skill. This DNP team hopes that our outline will be put to good use by a future DNP group in order to improve patient safety and maintain anesthesia providers' cricothyrotomy skills.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Iowa Model Revised

Figure 1

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Note. Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and Validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>

The image on the right indicates which portions of the IM will be omitted from our project.

Appendix B

Figure 2: Delphi Technique

Figure 2

Delphi Technique

Note. Adapted from the Delphi technique

Appendix C

Figure 3: How to Decide Appropriateness in 10 steps

Figure 3

Delphi methodology in healthcare research: How to decide appropriateness in 10 steps.

Note. Nasa, P., Jain, R., & Juneja, D. (2021). Delphi methodology in healthcare research:

How to decide its appropriateness. *World Journal of Methodology*, 11(4),116-129.

<https://doi.org/10.5662/wjm.v11.i4.116>

Appendix D

Figure 4: Evaluating Results

Delphi methodology in healthcare research: Evaluating results.

Note. Nasa, P., Jain, R., & Juneja, D. (2021). Delphi methodology in healthcare research: How to decide its appropriateness. *World Journal of Methodology*, 11(4),116-129.

<https://doi.org/10.5662/wjm.v11.i4.116>

Appendix E

First Delphi Round Questionnaire:

1. When was the last time you found yourself in a failed airway situation? (i.e., unable to mask ventilate, unable to place a supraglottic airway, unable to endotracheally intubate [] <6 months [] 6 months -2 years [] >2 years [] >10 years [] Never
2. In the event you were required to perform a cricothyrotomy, would you feel [] very poorly prepared [] poorly prepared [] well prepared [] very well prepared
3. When was the last time you received cricothyrotomy training? [] <6 months [] 6 months -2 years [] >2 years [] >10 years [] Never
4. On a scale of 0-4 (0 being poor, 4 being excellent), how would you rate the cricothyrotomy training you've received in the past?
5. On a scale of 0-4 (0 being no benefit, 4 being very beneficial), would additional cricothyrotomy training be beneficial to your practice?
6. If you have performed cricothyrotomy training in the past, please describe your experience.

Appendix F

Figure 5: KPSA IRB & CSUF IRB Approval- Exempt

Figure 5

CSUF IRB Approval

KPSA IRB Exempt

March 30, 2023

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Rachel McClanahan

Application No. HSR-22-23-318

Study Title: KPSA: Developing a Cricothyrotomy Training Module: A Delphi Analysis

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording).

Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office

InterOffice Memorandum

March 1, 2023

To: **Doctor Jeremy Heiner**
100 S Los Robles Ave., Suite 501
Pasadena, CA 91188

Re: Developing a Cricothyrotomy Training Module: A Delphi Analysis

Dear Dr. Heiner,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Armida Ayala".

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Appendix G

Figure 6: Delphi Analysis, First survey data

Figure 6

Delphi analysis, first round data

Q1 - When was the last time you found yourself in a failed airway situation? (i.e., unable to mask ventilate, unable to place a supraglottic airway, unable to endotracheally intubate)?

Q2 - How many times have you encountered a failed airway situation? (i.e., unable to mask ventilate, unable to place a supraglottic airway, unable to endotracheally intubate)

Q3 - In the event you were required to perform a cricothyrotomy, would you feel

Q4 - When was the last time you received cricothyrotomy training?

Q5 - On a scale of 0-4 (0 being poor, 4 being excellent), how would you rate the cricothyrotomy training you've received in the past?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Quality of cricothyrotomy training	0.00	4.00	2.16	1.50	2.24	19

Q6 - On a scale of 0-4 (0 being no benefit, 4 being very beneficial), would additional cricothyrotomy training be beneficial to your practice?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
---	-------	---------	---------	------	---------------	----------	-------

1	Benefit of training to anesthesia practice	1.00	4.00	3.5 3	0.88	0.78	19
---	--	------	------	----------	------	------	----

If you have received any cricothyrotomy training in the past, please describe your experience.

Kit/ dummy training in school

simulation

Our program obtained pig tracheas for our class to perform cricothyrotomies on using actual cricothyrotomy kits. I also ran the simulation lab for an anesthesia program and conducted the same simulations for several groups of students.

We did a lab at work in the school of nursing

Proctor showed steps with kit

none

Our department does training yearly. We used pig tracheas and cricothyrotomy kits last year and most recently we did it with a scalpel, bougie, ETT technique

Advanced Airway Conference where we practiced on 3D printed tracheas

Anesthesia conference with power point

Seminar where practiced with pig tracheas; lots of hands on

45-60 mins course - lecture with hand ons

KPSA/Heiner training

Appendix H

Figure 7: Key Themes

Figure 7

Key Themes

Key Themes

Non-Simulation Based Training (NSBT), Simulation Based Training (SBT)

Appendix I

Figure 8: Delphi Analysis, Second Round Survey Data

Figure 8

Delphi Analysis, Second Round Survey Data

Q1 - 1. Do you currently complete annual, online competency training for cricothyrotomy?

Q2 - 2. Would you be interested in attending an advanced airway course that was regularly offered, and included hands-on, simulated experience in performing cricothyrotomy?

Q3 - 3. How often would you prefer training with cricothyrotomy techniques?

Q4 - 4. Would you prefer training in:

Q5 - 5. How frequently do you spend time educating yourself on difficult or failed airway management outside of what is offered at your workplace?

Q6 - 6. Is there any other cricothyrotomy training you would like to receive? If “Yes” please explain

Simulation based training (SBT)

The data analysis was generated using Qualtrics software, Copyright ©2023 Qualtrics. Qualtrics and all other Qualtrics product or service names are registered trademarks or trademarks of Qualtrics, Provo, UT, USA. <https://www.qualtrics.com>

Appendix J

Delphi Analysis, Third Round Survey

Discussion Questions:

1. Is there any cricothyrotomy training you would like to receive? If “yes,” please explain.
2. What are key concepts you would include in a cricothyrotomy education and training module?
3. What are barriers to anesthesia providers receiving regular cricothyrotomy training?

Appendix K

Figure 9: Outline for Online Cricothyrotomy Education & Training Module

Figure 9

Outline for Online Cricothyrotomy Education & Training Module

Outline for Online Cricothyrotomy Education & Training Module

- 1) Education & Training Module Overview
 - a) Introduction
 - b) Purpose and Objectives
 - c) Define Cricothyrotomy Procedure
 - i) Relevant anatomy review
 - ii) Decision-making Process
 - iii) Techniques
 - d) Variables
 - e) Demonstration
- 2) Introduction
 - a) Background of Cricothyrotomy
 - i) Clinicians can experience a failed airway when an unexpected difficulty occurs during airway management and cannot mask ventilate, endotracheally intubate, or ventilate using a supraglottic airway device
 - ii) Difficult airway algorithms and failed airway checklists recommend emergency invasive airway (cricothyrotomy) when clinicians fail to establish adequate oxygenation and ventilation.
 - (1) ASA's Difficult Airway Algorithm: The ASA states that emergency invasive airway access should be performed when anesthesia providers find themselves in a failed airway situation
 - (2) DAS Failed Airway Algorithm: recommends surgical cricothyrotomy as the means to acquire emergency airway access
 - iii) The Decision to Perform a Cricothyrotomy
 - (1) The reluctance/hesitance to commit to performing a cricothyrotomy is often more detrimental to the patient than the procedure itself: delaying a procedure (when necessary) increases the mortality and morbidity risk to the patient.
 - (2) Avoidance of non-technical skills such as task management, teamwork, effective communication, situational awareness, and effective decision-making may lead to critically delayed airway interventions.
 - iv) High Acuity Low Occurrence (HALO) Airway Procedure:

- (1) A cricothyrotomy is categorized as a HALO procedure. HALO procedures are associated with provider uncertainty/hesitancy potentially resulting in delayed decision making and poor skills maintenance.
 - (2) The consequences of not being able to complete a cricothyrotomy when indicated can significantly contribute to adverse patient outcomes and provider liability.
 - (3) The three most common adverse effects of difficult airways are airway trauma, brain damage, and death.
- v) Educational gap identified in recent literature review.
- (1) Without frequent airway training, there is a significant decrease in skill performance, adherence to difficult airway algorithms, and medical decision-making.
 - (2) Deterioration of skill retention occurs across all airway management types, indicates a need for frequent training in order to maintain appropriate airway skills.
- b) Module Objectives
- i) Bridge the gap in cricothyrotomy education.
 - ii) Provide an effective cricothyrotomy training pedagogy for anesthesia providers.
- 3) Cricothyrotomy Procedure
- a) Relevant anatomy review
 - i) Use of visual aids, images, and anatomical models to show pertinent anatomical structures
 - ii) Identify key structures in the neck and anatomical landmarks important to successful cricothyrotomy.
 - (1) Thyroid cartilage with thyroid prominence
 - (a) AKA “Adam’s apple” in males. Prominent cartilage in the neck, good starting landmark.
 - (2) Cricoid cartilage
 - (a) Located caudad to the thyroid cartilage.
 - (b) Circumferential cartilage with large posterior portion that will act as a protective back stop when placing cricothyrotomy.
 - (3) Cricothyroid membrane
 - (a) Target for cricothyrotomy airway access
 - (b) Depression between the thyroid cartilage and the cricoid cartilage.

- (c) Emphasis on location and how to properly identify since literature review shows that providers commonly misidentify the cricothyroid membrane.

(4) Trachea

- (a) Explain the structure and functions of trachea and how it is the passageway below the glottis to the lungs.
- (b) Describe length of average trachea as it pertains to the depth of insertion of endotracheal tubes used for cricothyrotomy.
- (c) Emphasize the distinct differences between subcutaneous tissue and tracheal tissue as there are often reports of a false passage creation resulting in misplacement and the potential for significant morbidity and mortality when not correctly placed in the trachea.
 - (i) Anterior tracheal rings are palpable from within the airway.

(5) Major blood vessels

- (a) The cricothyroid artery, a branch of the superior thyroid artery, is anterior and superior to the cricothyroid membrane.
 - (i) If lacerated can result in bleeding when accessing the cricothyroid membrane.

b) Decision making process

- i) Use of established cognitive aids and difficult airway algorithms should be used to assist providers with the decision to perform a cricothyrotomy.
- ii) Difficult airway algorithm review
 - (1) American Society of Anesthesiologists Difficult Airway Algorithm
 - (a) Traditionally taught in USA
 - (b) Review of 2022 difficult airway algorithm
 - (i) Latest version emphasizes awareness of time and limiting the number of attempts and devices before attempting to access airway via cricothyrotomy.
 - (c) Emergency airway access, the final pathway of the ASA difficult airway algorithm includes surgical front of neck access, cricothyrotomy.
 - (2) Difficult Airway Society Difficult intubation guidelines
 - (a) Overview of difficult intubation guidelines
 - (b) Advantageous due to its simplicity
 - (c) Review of 2015 difficult intubation guidelines

- (i) emphasis on limited attempts before declaring cannot intubate, cannot oxygenate scenario.
 - (ii) Emphasis on bougie assisted surgical cricothyrotomy.
 - iii) Importance of Anesthesia Non-Technical Skills
 - (1) Situational awareness
 - (a) Studies show that healthcare providers tend to get stuck on tasks and will continue to try unsuccessful techniques over and over again.
 - (b) Difficult airway algorithms recognize this potential for error and now emphasize the importance of time and limiting airway instrumentation with the different airway adjuncts before advancing to a cricothyrotomy to attain airway access.
 - (2) Communication
 - (a) Difficult airway algorithms emphasize the importance of announcing to the healthcare team when there is a cannot oxygenate, cannot intubate scenario.
 - (b) Allows help to come and alerts everyone to the situation.
 - (3) Leadership
 - (a) The anesthesia provider should communicate the situation, assign tasks, and lead the interventions to access the patient's airway.
 - (b) Similar role to ACLS
 - (4) Decision making under stress.
 - (a) Use of cognitive aids and simpler algorithms lead to improved outcomes (Ambardekar et al. 2019).
- c) Techniques
 - i) Bougie-Assisted Surgical Cricothyrotomy
 - (1) Equipment available in every OR: Scalpel, bougie stylet, size 6.0 ETT
 - (2) Identify cricothyroid membrane with: Laryngeal handshake, sternal notch to cricoid cartilage, or point of care ultrasound (POCUS)
 - (3) Technique:
 - (a) Transverse stab through cricothyroid membrane
 - (b) Incise the length of the cricothyroid membrane
 - (c) Remove blade
 - (d) Insert nondominant hand index finger through cricothyroid membrane incision

- (e) Insert bougie through cricothyroid membrane incision and over the pad of the index finger.
 - (f) Stop advancing the bougie when there is “hold-up” or resistance.
 - (g) Railroad 6.0mm cuffed endotracheal tube over the bougie and into the trachea until the ETT cuff disappears through the cricothyroid membrane incision.
 - (h) Inflate ETT cuff and ventilate, confirming proper placement with end tidal CO₂.
 - (i) Secure ETT.
- (4) Impalpable cricothyroid membrane
- (a) Make 8-10cm vertical incision (cephalad to caudad)
 - (b) Use nondominant hand index finger to dissect tissue and identify larynx and cricothyroid membrane.
 - (c) Proceed as you would with palpable cricothyroid membrane.
- ii) Wire-guided cricothyrotomy
- (1) Melker cricothyrotomy kit
 - (a) Equipment : Melker kit
 - (i) Consists of airway, scalpel, syringe, introducer needle, wire guide, curved dilator
 - (2) Identify cricothyroid membrane with : Laryngeal handshake, sternal notch to cricoid cartilage, or point of care ultrasound (POCUS)
 - (3) Technique: Achieved using percutaneous entry (Selinger technique) via the cricothyroid membrane.
 - a) Attach a syringe halfway filled with saline or water to the end of the introducer needle.
 - b) Insert needle at a 90-degree angle as the posterior lamina of cricoid cartilage.
 - a. Less likely to puncture posterior wall of the trachea with 90-degree angle.
 - c) Confirm placement of needle into trachea by aspirating and noting air bubbles in the syringe.
 - d) Advance wire guide through the introducer needle
 - e) Remove the needle over the wire, leaving the wire in place.
 - f) Stab incision with scalpel
 - g) Advance the dilator and airway over the wire, ensuring the wire remains stable to not inadvertently misplace the dilator.

- h) Place dilator/airway unit into trachea over the wire (may require twisting motion).
 - i) Remove the dilator and wire together from the airway.
 - j) Inflate cuff on airway.
 - k) Ventilate and ensure proper placement with ET CO_2 verification.
 - l) Secure airway.
- iii) Needle cricothyrotomy
- (1) Should be used on pediatric patients <10 years old.
 - (2) Provides temporary airway.
 - (3) Equipment:
 - (a) Large bore catheter
 - (i) 16g or larger
 - (ii) Preferably a catheter made for cricothyrotomy
 - (b) Trans tracheal jet ventilator
 - (4) Technique:
 - (a) Attach a syringe halfway filled with saline or water to the end of the large bore catheter and needle.
 - (b) Insert needle at a 90-degree angle as the posterior lamina of cricoid cartilage.
 - (i) Less likely to puncture posterior wall of the trachea with 90-degree angle.
 - (c) Aspirate air into syringe to confirm placement within the trachea.
 - (d) One person is assigned to the job of holding the catheter in place. That is their only job.
 - (5) Angio catheters versus cricothyrotomy specific needles
 - (a) Angio catheters should be avoided whenever possible.
 - (i) designed to go into veins and soften up when inserted into vein.
 - (ii) When Angio catheter is placed into a warm neck it will soften and has more potential for malfunction.
 - (b) Cricothyrotomy needles should be accessible, when possible, they do not soften up and remain rigid after placement.
 - (i) Some types can be connected to a circuit or to jet ventilation.
 - (6) Transtracheal jet-ventilation
 - (a) Adds complexity to the needle cricothyrotomy.
 - (b) Required to provide needed airway pressure to ventilate through a small catheter.

(c) Insufflate to 20-25 PSI (do not exceed 50 PSI)

(d) Complications

(i) If not holding catheter well, the catheter will be ejected with the high pressure of trans tracheal jet ventilation.

(ii) Subcutaneous emphysema

(iii) Hypercarbia: ensure patent airway for exhalation.

1. place OPA and NPA if needed.

d) Complications and management

i) Common complications:

(1) Lacerated cricothyroid membrane blood vessels

(a) Practitioners should be aware of the potential for bleeding when placing a cricothyrotomy.

(b) Laceration of the cricothyroid artery on the superior border of cricothyroid membrane will cause large amount of blood in surgical field.

(c) After a cricothyrotomy airway is secured, apply pressure to bleeding areas, use hemostatic agents if needed.

(i) Consult general or ENT surgeon since cricothyrotomy sites should have urgent surgical revision after airway is secured.

(2) Misplaced tracheal tube

(a) False passages between the skin or subcutaneous tissue and the trachea may be created when attempting to access the trachea lumen via the cricothyroid membrane.

(b) Confirm proper placement by palpating the cricoid cartilage posterior lamina during a assisted surgical cricothyrotomy.

(c) Confirm proper placement when using wire guided or need cricothyrotomy technique by aspirating air into syringe, which confirms the needle is in the trachea.

(d) Auscultate for lung sounds, verify ETCO₂, view misting within tracheal tube, observe chest rise and fall, and palpate bag compliance after cricothyrotomy airway is placed to ensure proper placement.

(3) Infection

(a) Clean the skin with betadine, chlorhexidine, or an alcohol swab before placing cricothyrotomy if time allows.

(b) Monitor for signs and symptoms of surgical site infection after airway placement.

(4) Pneumothorax

- (a) Occurs when air enters the chest cavity from a potential bronchial perforation or by barotrauma with needle cricothyrotomy and jet ventilation.
- (b) If pneumothorax occurs, patient will require chest tube placement on the affected side.

4) Variables

- a) Team member's availability: Emergency Department Physicians, ENT surgeons, team model
- b) Equipment available in every OR: Scalpel, bougie, ETT.
- c) Providers should become aware what equipment is available in the operating room in which they work.

5) Demonstration

- a) At this point in the module there should be a video played that shows a real-life situation cricothyrotomy. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1iPRrzO26eI>
- b) Simulation training
 - i) 3D printed models
 - (1) Use of 3D printed trainers for techniques listed above.
 - ii) Porcine trachea
 - (1) Use of porcine trachea for techniques listed above.
 - iii) Full simulation training
 - (1) Full simulation
 - (2) Scenario
 - (a) CICO situation
 - (b) Vital signs start to deteriorate.
 - (c) Provider must make decision to perform cricothyrotomy.
 - (d) Provider must decide which technique to use.
 - (e) Practice anesthesia non-technical skills
 - (i) Provider should call for help, announce CICO situation.
 - (ii) Assign roles.
 - (iii) Placement of surgical airway